

The Job Satisfaction of the Employees with the Organization Retention of Metropolitan Waterworks Authority at Bangkok

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Abstract—This research aimed to study correlation between work satisfaction and organization core value of officers in Waterworks Authority, Bangkok Branch. Sample group of the study was 112 officers who worked in the Waterworks Authority, Bangkok Branch. Questionnaires were employed as a research tools, while, Percentage, Mean, Standard Deviation, T-test, One-way ANOVA, and Pearson Product Moment Correlation were claimed as statistics used in this study. Researcher found that overall and individual aspects of work satisfaction namely, work characteristic, work progress, and colleagues significantly correlated with organization core value in aspect of perception in choice of work at 0.5, 0.01, and 0.01 respectively. Also, such aspects were compatible with income at .05 which indicated the low level of correlation, mid low correlation respectively at the same direction, same direction, opposite direction, and same direction, correspondingly.

Keywords—Employee of Bangkok branch, Job Satisfaction, the organization Retention.

I. INTRODUCTION

PERSONNEL were claimed as one type of resources which was not only unpredictable comparing to other types of resource such as technology and finance, but they also cost high expenses. Therefore, human resources demanded efficient management in order to provide satisfaction and met works requirements which finally led to organization success [1]. Factor that supported officers to eagerly response to organization goals was motivation. Comparing one enthusiastic offer to the fatigue one, such behaviors derived from individual motivation both internal and external which had external stimulus as their origin. Such stimulus referred to various situations of organization both in physical and social [2] which encouraged officers to employ their abilities to the best and persuaded them to work with the organization as long as possible by fostering organization pride and zero turnover rate since high resignation rate tended to increase administrative cost.

Good governance should consist of human and organization development in parallel since both of them were equally essential. Proper organizational design took part in desirable work environment and encouraged workers to perform their best qualities. In the area of private sector and public enterprises including bureaucratic and educational segment, capitalism was highly influential in those areas which led to

organizational adjustment in order to increase competitiveness and sustainability. Theoretically, capitalism referred to finance, resources, management, competitive ability, technology, knowledge, health, and value of individuals. However, the idea recently revolves much more around humans because they are one of the factors that potentially bring the organization to advantaged position. Such notion is claimed as human capital [3]. Human Capital Management--HCM referred to the management aiming to provide quality and individual efficiency rather than group management which dictated and searched for talented individuals. In order to retain employee and motivate them to bring the best performance, operators involving in HCM need to be creative and aim to excellency especially, in aspect of employee motivation and employee retention. Therefore, appropriate human resources management tends to flourish organizational expansion due to human potentials. Also proper condition, training, and development can foster the ability of humans to highly employ their knowledge and to be capable to serve the organization which includes the readiness to face the change. Additionally, the focus on employee retention with good quality of life both physically and mentally plus the safety and desirable environment tend to increase workers satisfaction which took part in the idea of "Organization Excellency [4]"

As stated in prior, human resources management in new era requires flexible and changeable models which focus more on results rather than process or procedure. In addition, the operation of involved parties, namely employees, employers, administrator, and human resource office need to be clearly categorized. Moreover, criteria regarding personnel must be improved starting from recruitment and selection procedure, potential development, welfare, income, to motivation in order to satisfy the workers. As a result, the organizations can successfully retain their employees.

Presently, several organizations encounter the problem with regards to employee retention. More and more of them chose to resign due to the lack of motivation. To decrease the rising turnover rate and encourage employees to work in organization, target group categorization and efficient strategy are needed including proper plan and assessment.

To retain employees and persuade them to develop themselves as well as devote to organizations, motivation and sense of belonging are the issues needed to keep in mind. The organization must create the atmosphere fostering those characteristics to their employees. Therefore, the study of organizational behavior at personal level which consists of

perception, attitude, value, and empowerment are essential in behavioral change. Solution subsequently is to the answer the question on how to encourage members to physically and mentally devote to organization. Additionally, it is important to make them recognize that they are also owner and stakeholder of the organizations.

Waterworks authority recognized that good governance is basic factor for operating organization. In order to continue making sustainable progress of the authority and to ensure transparent, efficient, and fair management, waterworks authority presently pay attention to internal audit and risk management so that sub committees are established in order to regulate the organization in social and environmental aspect.

Waterworks authority, Bangkean Branch locates at 1/103 Moo 6 Chaeng Wattana Rd. Anusawarechaisamoraphoome District Bangkean, Bangkok. Responsible areas are 93 m² with 101,713 clients. Water produced by Bangkean waterworks deliver to public 24 hours a day. The authority continuously improve its services basing on metropolitan waterworks policy in order satisfy clients which can be categorized in 2 groups namely, personal accommodation, industry, and others. Recommendations by clients are as followed. Waterworks authority should deliver service with deftness and speed which is compatible with government policy.

Therefore, researcher is interested in studying satisfaction and employee retention of Waterworks officers, Bangkean Branch. Research results subsequently are used as source of information to amend authority's policy and to be a model of creating job satisfaction for employees. Also, such information is used in order to make a plan and design strategy to retain employees for the waterworks authority, Bangkean Branch.

II. METHODOLOGY

A. Research Objectives

To study correlation between work satisfaction and employee retention of waterworks officers, Bangkean Branch.

B. Research Hypothesis

Work satisfaction has correlated with employees retention of waterworks officers, Bangkean Branch.

C. Research Scope

In this research, researcher aimed to study work satisfaction and employee retention. The research scope was as followed.

1. Population and Sample

Population referred to 156 waterworks officers, Bangkean Branch

Sample referred to 112 waterworks officers, Bangkean Branch by mean of proposional stratified random sampling

2. Content

Independent variables consist of Personal information which are gender, age, income, work status, educational background, marital status and work experiences and work satisfaction which are satisfaction in aspects of job

description, income, progression, chief of divisions and colleagues.

Dependent Variables referred to employees retention of waterworks officers, Bangkean Branch consisting of turnover intention of employee, sense of belonging, perception of other job opportunities

3. Time

Data collection was committed in 2012.

D. Conceptual Framework

In studying employee retention of waterwork officer, Bangkean Branch, research scope was as followed.

Fig. 1 Conceptual Framework

Research samples referred to 156 waterworks officers, Bangkean Branch selected and calculated by mean of Taro Yamane formula [5] with 95% of reliability and not exceed 5% of acceptable tolerances.

Therefore, research samples consisted of 112 individuals with 10% of substitutes = $(112 \times 10 / 100) = 11$ in order to prevent any mistakes. Overall in summary participants were 123 individuals.

III. FINDING

Research results can be concluded as followed

1) Work satisfaction in overall and employee retention in aspect of non-turnover intention of waterworks authority, Bangkean Branch had significant correlation at .05, while in aspects of job description and colleagues were at .01 complying with hypothesis mentioned above. The relation was at low, low, and medium respectively in the same direction. It can be claimed that if waterworks officers of Bangkean branch overall satisfied with their works and highly satisfied with individual aspects referring to job description and colleagues, employee retention in aspects of non-turnover tend to increase.

However, income, work progression, and non-turnover intention of waterworks officers, Bangkean Branch were not correlated.

2) Overall satisfaction and in individual aspect referred to job description and colleagues significantly correlated with sense of belonging at .01 that comply with hypothesis mentioned above. Those factors were significantly correlated at average level, average level, and average level, respectively and also in the same direction. This mean that the more satisfaction the waterworks officers in Bangkean Branch expressed on their work in overall and on job description plus

colleagues, the more sense of belonging they feel for the organization.

Nevertheless, income, work progression, and the chief of division had no correlation with employee retention in this case.

3) Overall work satisfaction had significant correlation with non-turnover intention at .05 and also had correlation with individual aspects, namely job description, work progression, and colleagues at .01 complying with hypothesis mentioned in prior. Those factors hold correlation in low, low, average, and average, respectively in the same direction, in the same direction, in the opposite direction, and in the same direction. It mean that the more satisfaction the waterworks officers Bangkean Branch expressed on their work in overall and in individual aspects namely, job description and colleagues, the more employee retention in aspect of perception on non – turnover rate tend to increase. Also, if such satisfaction reflect the higher rate of work progression, non-turnover rate was likely to decrease.

Still, factors such as income and chief superior had no correlation with perception of non-turnover in this case.

4) Overall work satisfaction and individual aspects, namely job description, work progression, and colleagues had correlation at .01, while it also had correlation with income at .05 complying with hypothesis stated prior. The relation expressed in average, average, low, and average, respectively in the same direction. It can be claimed that the more waterworks officers satisfied their work in overall and in individual aspects namely, job description and colleagues, retention rate supposed to increase.

However, work progression, chief of division, and employee retention were not correlated in this case.

IV. RECOMMENDATION AND FUTURE STUDIES

According to research results, researcher would like to recommend as follows;

- 1) The incomes should be competency base since it will be more reasonable and likely to fulfill organizations objectives rather than focusing on specific qualities of employee such as talent, moral issues, and job specification. This is because competency base pay attention on all qualities of employee referred to motivation, characteristics, belief, value, and attitudes affecting accomplishment of the work. Still, income with competency base is not universal solution. Consideration with regards to vision, value, mission, structure, goal, culture, and politics inside the organizations are needed to keep in mind. Additionally, competency based model should be adapted in every part of human resources instead of applying only on income. Such idea plus *proper* strategy and criteria in the organization will increase employee retention rate which lead to the accomplishment of the organization.
- 2) The organization should improve non-income payment system especially, non – benefit income in order to comply with employee demand. This will motivate capable workers to improve their performance.

Additionally, survey regarding employees' need should be done. Results of such survey can be used as a source of information in order to consider annual policy in aspects of income and non-income benefit comparing with other organizations such as Electricity Generating Authority of Thailand. In this consideration, non-income benefits such as accommodation, transportation, recreational activities, uniforms, training, provident fund, compensation benefit, and pensions are needed to take into account. Those benefits supposed to make employees satisfy and continue working for the organization.

- 3) Responsible tasks should be properly assign as well as the delegation. Workloads should not be heavily put on individual employees. Moreover, the organization might leave the opportunity for employees both admins and technicians to put imagination on their work.
- 4) The organization should offer opportunities in aspects of education, training, seminar, promotion, and rotation in equal and fair manner. In addition, sense of security must be marked as the important issue so that activities such as recreation should be provided for employee in order to relieve stress due to daily work. Moreover, employee could be encouraged to interchange their information regards their works, criteria, procedure in their jobs in order to understand each other which can build the co-operation among the workers.
- 5) The organization should provide a plan regarding career path for employees as following details.
- 6) Traditional career path expresses job position in vertical. Promotion lines up in current division or department in step by step procedure.

Network career path expresses job position in vertical, while promotion lines up in horizontal by mean of transferring or rotating with interchangeable experiences.

Dual career path expresses job position in vertical, while promotion lines up in current department by comparing individual positions in the same level.

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